

1 **A theoretical approach to prevention of disease early in etiology through use of CDK4/6 inhibitors.**

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6 A theoretical approach to prevention of disease early in etiology through use of CDK4/6 inhibitors to
7 induce synthetic lethality in cells undergoing malignant transformation to chronic disease to prevent onset
8 of disease based on transcriptomic-based preventative diagnostics.

9 Citations

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